

Rogier Floors & RAM (rofl@dtu.dk)

Validation of (Py)WAsP for wind resource assessment and numerical wind atlases

When developing a model, we need an objective measure to quantify model performance

- **Metric:**
 - $P = \frac{1}{2}\rho U^3$
- **Uncertainty:**
 - Input uncertainty
 - Model uncertainty
 - User uncertainty (can user easily make mistakes?)

Different WAsP core versions

WAsP versions that had changes in core

- WAsP 12.0 air density
- WAsP 12.6 baroclinicity ERA5
- WAsP 12.7 displacement heights
- WAsP 12.8 stability
- WAsP 12.x polygons
- WAsP 12.x histogram

Cross predictions

- Many old DTU and external data converted to single format:
 - Windkit "binned wind climate" points
- Use WAsP core with `cross_predict` function from PyWAsP:
 - Using wind climate from 1 height and prediction to
 - other height (vertical extrapolation)
 - other mast (horizontal extrapolation)

Signature:

```
cross_predict(  
    data_dir,  
    filename,  
    include_self_predictions=True,  
    nsamples=0,  
    zrange=None,  
    onlyup=False,  
    model='WAsP_12.10',
```

	name	x	y	epsg	elevmap	roumap	lctable	stab_source	baro_source
group									
WM01	WM01	662743.2	6834989.4	32733	WM01.map	WM01.map	NaN	ERA5	ERA5
WM02	WM02	344361.1	6511054.9	32734	WM02.map	WM02.map	NaN	ERA5	ERA5
WM03	WM03	255549.9	6486539.1	32734	WM03.map	WM03.map	NaN	ERA5	ERA5
WM04	WM04	229440.3	6362045.0	32734	WM04.map	WM04.map	NaN	ERA5	ERA5
WM05	WM05	380119.2	6169215.6	32734	WM05.map	WM05.map	NaN	ERA5	ERA5
WM06	WM06	471013.8	6397802.7	32734	WM06.map	WM06.map	NaN	ERA5	ERA5
WM07	WM07	645479.5	6351326.6	32734	WM07.map	WM07.map	NaN	ERA5	ERA5
WM08	WM08	270725.8	6222861.2	32735	WM08.map	WM08.map	NaN	ERA5	ERA5
WM09	WM09	312257.8	6540733.5	32735	WM09.map	WM09.map	NaN	ERA5	ERA5

Validation dataset

- 160 masts with at least 2 heights
- Some of them multiple masts, allowing horizontal cross predictions
- 131 with RIX < 1%
- Right now, we can only validate U, since the measurements do not contain temperature or pressure (required for ρ)

WAsP 12.0 Better estimations of air density ($\frac{1}{2}\rho U^3$)

Article

Estimating Air Density Using Observations and Re-Analysis Outputs for Wind Energy Purposes

Rogier Floors* and Morten Nielsen

DTU Wind Energy, Technical University of Denmark, Risø Campus, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark; nini@dtu.dk

* Correspondence: rofl@dtu.dk; Tel.: +45-4480-5090

Received: 26 April 2019; Accepted: 23 May 2019; Published: 28 May 2019

Abstract: A method to estimate air density as a function of elevation for wind energy resource assessments is presented. The current practice of using nearby measurements of pressure and temperature is compared with a method that uses re-analysis data. It is found that using re-analysis data to estimate air density gives similar or smaller mean absolute errors compared to using measurements that were on average located 40 km away. A method to interpolate power curves that are valid for different air densities is presented. The new model is implemented in the industry-standard model for wind resource assessment and compared with the current version of that model and shown to lead to more accurate assessment of the air density at different elevations.

Keywords: air density; wind energy; power curves; WAsP; ERA5; CFSR

<https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/12/11/2038>

Table 1. Summary error metrics from the methods presented in this paper. The modelled and observed air density at site i of the total number of sites $N = 77$ are denoted as x_i and y_i , respectively. Then, the mean absolute error is defined as $\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |100(y_i - x_i) / x_i|$, the correlation coefficient $R = \frac{1}{\sigma_x \sigma_y} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})$, where the overbar and σ denote the mean and standard deviation, respectively.

Method	Mean Abs. Error (%)	R
WAsP 11	0.203	0.9975
IEC 61400–12–1	0.185	0.9977
WAsP 12	0.186	0.9977
WAsP 12 CFSR	0.241	0.9987
WAsP 12 ERA5	0.127	0.9993
WAsP 12 ERA5 L	0.114	0.9994

input

+

model

+

user

WAsP 12.6 geostrophic shear model ($|\overline{\epsilon_p}| = 6.9\%$)

DTU

Implementation of large-scale average geostrophic wind shear in WAsP 12.1

https://orbit.dtu.dk/files/149165080/e_report_0169.pdf

WAsP 12.7 displacement heights ($|\overline{\epsilon_p}| = 6.7\%$)

Wind Energ. Sci., 6, 1379–1400, 2021
<https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-6-1379-2021>
 © Author(s) 2021. This work is distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.

Satellite-based estimation of roughness lengths and displacement heights for wind resource modelling

Rogier Floors¹, Merete Badger¹, Ib Troen¹, Kenneth Grogan², and Finn-Hendrik Permien³

¹DTU Wind Energy, Risø Campus, Technical University of Denmark, Frederiksborgvej 399, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark

²DHI GRAS A/S, Agern Alle 5, 2970 Hørsholm, Denmark

³Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy A/S, Borupvej 16, 7330 Brande, Denmark

Correspondence: Rogier Floors (rofl@dtu.dk)

Received: 30 March 2021 – Discussion started: 6 April 2021

Revised: 10 September 2021 – Accepted: 30 September 2021 – Published: 4 November 2021

Abstract. Wind turbines in northern Europe are frequently placed in forests, which sets new wind resource modelling requirements. Accurate mapping of the land surface can be challenging at forested sites due to sudden transitions between patches with very different aerodynamic properties, e.g. tall trees, clearings, and lakes. Tree growth and deforestation can lead to temporal changes of the forest. Global or pan-European land cover data sets fail to resolve these forest properties, aerial lidar campaigns are costly and infrequent, and manual digitization is labour-intensive and subjective. Here, we investigate the potential of using satellite observations to characterize the land surface in connection with wind energy flow modelling using the Wind Atlas Analysis and Application

<https://wes.copernicus.org/articles/6/1379/2021/>

WAsP 12.8 new stability model ($|\overline{\epsilon_p}| = 4.6\%$)

Boundary-Layer Meteorology (2023) 188:75–101
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10546-023-00803-3>

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Using Observed and Modelled Heat Fluxes for Improved Extrapolation of Wind Distributions

Rogier Floors¹ · Ib Troen¹ · Alfredo Peña¹

Received: 1 October 2022 / Accepted: 9 March 2023 / Published online: 20 April 2023
 © The Author(s) 2023

Abstract

Modelling the horizontal and vertical variation of wind speed is crucial for wind energy applications. A model frequently used for this purpose is part of the Wind Atlas Analysis and Application program (WAsP). Here, we modify the model in WAsP to account for local atmospheric stability parameters. Atmospheric stability effects are treated by using the impact of a temperature scale on the geostrophic drag law and the diabatic logarithmic wind profile. Using this approach, wind-direction dependent mean and standard deviation of a surface-layer temperature scale and a mean boundary-layer height scale can be obtained from either numerical weather prediction model output or observations to improve vertical extrapolations

<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10546-023-00803-3>

WAsP 12.x histogram transformations ($\overline{|\epsilon_p|} = 4.3\%$)

pywasp.wasp.predict_bwc

```
pywasp.wasp.predict_bwc(bwc, topo_map, output_locs, conf=None, n_sectors=None,
interp_method='given', input_mesoclimate=None, output_mesoclimate=None,
mesoclimate_interp_method='nearest', return_site_effects=False, add_met=True, cfd_volume=None,
bin_width=1.0, n_gbins=500) [source]
```

Predict a binned wind climate from a binned wind climate using a topography map for given output locations

Warning

This function is experimental and its signature may change.

- Parameters:
- `bwc` (`xarray.Dataset`) – PyWASP `xr.Dataset` containing wind climate to be generalized
 - `topo_map` (`TopographyMap`) – `TopographyMap` of the region to model
 - `output_locs` (`xarray.Dataset`) – Output locations in one of the windkit spatial structures (point, stacked_point, cuboid)
 - `conf` (`Config`, *optional*) – PyWASP configuration object
 - `n_sectors` (`int`, *optional*) – Number of sector for which the terrain is analyzed. By default, the same number of sectors as the provided `bwc`
 - `generalization_method` (`{"geostrophic", "idealized"}`) – By default "geostrophic". i.e use a binned geostrophic wind climate as intermediate

WAsP 12.x polygon maps

user

Vertical extrapolation errors

- Aggregated all cross predictions by vertical difference between source and target
- The smaller the vertical distance the smaller the error
- Largest differences at large extrapolations distances for new WAsP stability model

Horizontal extrapolation errors

- The larger the horizontal distance the larger the error
- Only based on 11 sites

Validation report

- The output of the cross prediction script are 2 datasets *pred* and *obs*
- Package *wind-validation* can be used to create a simple report to explore results
- The plan is to make this reporting the part of the CI, so that it can be automatically published for a new pywasp version
- See pywasp, windkit and wind-validation at
 - <https://docs.wasp.dk/>

Wind-Validation Comparison Weibull Report

Summary Tables

Validation was produced on 2025-11-15 at 21:41:07 using wind-validation version: 0.1.dev335+gd7f1ac4b9. This report gives an validation summary over multiple validation results to compare how different models perform on the same datasets. This report was made for 391 points obtained at 131 masts.

Table 1.1: The comparison results of the Obs. vs WAsP_12.6 validation for 391 points. Observed and Predicted are the mean observed and modelled values, respectively. ME is the mean error, RMSE is the root mean square error, MAE and MAPE are the mean absolute error. The power density values are calculated for standard air density 1.225 kg/m³.

Variable	Observed	Predicted	Mean error (bias)	Mean abs error	Mean abs percentage error
Wind speed	7.3 m/s	7.4 m/s	0.1 m/s	0.2 m/s	2.5 %
Power density	515.3 W/m ²	528.4 W/m ²	13.0 W/m ²	27.4 W/m ²	6.9 %

Table 1.2: Same table as Table 1.1 but for model WAsP_12.7.

Variable	Observed	Predicted	Mean error (bias)	Mean abs error	Mean abs percentage error
Wind speed	7.3 m/s	7.4 m/s	0.1 m/s	0.2 m/s	2.4 %
Power density	515.3 W/m ²	529.5 W/m ²	14.1 W/m ²	27.0 W/m ²	6.7 %

Table 1.3: Same table as Table 1.1 but for model WAsP_12.8.

Variable	Observed	Predicted	Mean error (bias)	Mean abs error	Mean abs percentage error
Wind speed	7.3 m/s	7.3 m/s	-0.0 m/s	0.1 m/s	1.9 %
Power density	515.3 W/m ²	522.4 W/m ²	7.1 W/m ²	20.5 W/m ²	4.6 %

Table 1.4: Same table as Table 1.1 but for model WAsP_12.11.

Variable	Observed	Predicted	Mean error (bias)	Mean abs error	Mean abs percentage error
Wind speed	7.3 m/s	7.3 m/s	-0.0 m/s	0.1 m/s	1.8 %
Power density	515.3 W/m ²	518.4 W/m ²	3.1 W/m ²	18.7 W/m ²	4.3 %

Wind atlases can also be validated

- All sites automatically extracted from zarr dataset with GWC's

roumap	lctable	stab_source	baro_source	gwc
ESA_CCI	ESA_CCI.json	ERA5	ERA5	/work/users/neda/libfiles.zarr
ESA_CCI	ESA_CCI.json	ERA5	ERA5	/work/users/neda/libfiles.zarr
ESA_CCI	ESA_CCI.json	ERA5	ERA5	/work/users/neda/libfiles.zarr
ESA_CCI	ESA_CCI.json	ERA5	ERA5	/work/users/neda/libfiles.zarr
ESA_CCI	ESA_CCI.json	ERA5	ERA5	/work/users/neda/libfiles.zarr

Wind-Validation Comparison Weibull Report

Summary Tables

Validation was produced on 2025-11-15 at 22:25:28 using wind-validation version: 0.1.dev335+gd7f1ac4b9. This report gives an validation summary over multiple validation results to compare how different models perform on the same datasets. This report was made for 363 points obtained at 157 masts.

Table 1.1: The comparison results of the Obs. vs open_sites_GWA3_new00 validation for 363 points. Observed and Predicted are the mean observed and modelled values, respectively. ME is the mean error, RMSE is the root mean square error, MAE and MAPE are the mean absolute error. The power density values are calculated for standard air density 1.225 kg/m³.

Variable	Observed	Predicted	Mean error (bias)	Mean abs error	Mean abs percentage error
Wind speed	6.9 m/s	7.2 m/s	0.3 m/s	0.7 m/s	12.1 %
Power density	452.0 W/m ²	531.0 W/m ²	79.0 W/m ²	125.4 W/m ²	50.3 %

Table 1.2: Same table as Table 1.1 but for model open_sites_GWA4_lib_new03.

Variable	Observed	Predicted	Mean error (bias)	Mean abs error	Mean abs percentage error
Wind speed	6.9 m/s	7.1 m/s	0.2 m/s	0.6 m/s	9.9 %
Power density	452.0 W/m ²	475.0 W/m ²	23.1 W/m ²	98.5 W/m ²	32.7 %

Summary map

GWA validation results

- Mean abs error in power density:
 - GWA3: 50.3 %
 - GWA4: 32.7 %

Conclusions

- Cross prediction and validation datasets indispensable for developing new model version
- Significant decrease in input, model and user errors since WAsP 12.0
- Numerical wind atlases can now also be validated using the same framework

DTU

